

Learning from the Experience of COVID-19 Pandemic in Tanzania

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has profoundly influenced social, economic, and public health landscapes globally, and Tanzania is no exception. This article examines the moral implications its moral response to the crisis and what the government should do for future pandemics.

It explores the multifaceted moral responses elicited by the COVID-19 pandemic in Tanzania, emphasizing the origin, meaning, and significance of human life within the context of both a culture of life and a culture of death. It delves into the stewardship of life, analyzing the moral responsibilities individuals and societies hold in safeguarding health and well-being. The article starkly highlighted the Covid 19 as one of the many causes of deaths in Tanzania and Africa at large, and other causes like those that are manmade like abortion. Hence presenting a complex picture that intertwines healthcare access to pandemics, economic stability, and social cohesion.

The impacts of lockdowns are scrutinized, revealing the intricate balance between public health measures and their socioeconomic repercussions, particularly on vulnerable populations in Tanzania. The article also addresses the death tolls, the puzzling nature, effectiveness of vaccine rollouts, and the perceived worth of life amid such crises. Through these discussions, the narrative underscores the fear of death that has paralyzed many, stifling the courage to live fully.

Ultimately, this reflection seeks to project a message of hope beyond the grave, urging an understanding of life's intrinsic value and the importance of resilience in such times of crisis. By learning from the COVID-19 experience, Tanzania and Africa can cultivate a more profound appreciation for life, encouraging proactive measures to preserve health with an African approach and vitality in future crises. This moral examination invokes a collective call to transcend fear and embrace a renewed commitment to life, fostering a culture anchored in hope and human dignity.

Introduction

"Lord if you had been here, my brother would not have died." (Jn, 11:21-45).

One might ask, whether it is relevant to speak of COVID 19 in Tanzania and Africa at large while cases of COVID - 19 are now minimum. The answer is that infections are recurrent, and the reason is due to:

"Many factors such as changes in demography, lifestyle and agriculture are cited as a cause of emerging infectious diseases. Considered also are the general principles of bacterial and viral genetics which influence the emergence or re-emergence of microbes and the waxing and waning of epidemics as biological expressions of host-microbe associations. Lifestyle, and

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agriculture are cited as a cause of immersing infectious diseases" [5].

The reality is that COVID - 19 virus is still with us and is still taking the lives of people. According to the WHO; "COVID - 19 is still a "thing" in 2024 and should be taken seriously. This virus remains a persistent public health threat" [14]. As human beings, we are all affected by the cultures of life and death and we cannot avoid it, because we live, and at an unknown time we shall cease to exist. We are mortal beings. Death is the one subject of which no creature on earth can claim to have an experience about it. All those who attempt to discuss about death, does it through the knowledge from the other. None of us has any personal available memories on death. All humanity remains irresistible before death. It has led man to reflect and think same time a problem, but all in all death remains a mystery. It is in this context that death remains a fact to be accepted with humility. In a Biological point of view, death is natural, while in a supernatural point of view death is a fact known only by faith.

The Meaning of Culture

Culture is the characteristics and knowledge of a particular group of people, encompassing language, religion, cuisine, social habits music and arts. It is a general way of life.

Culture (Lat.: *Colere-cultivate*). Originally meant (1) the cultivation and development of human powers beyond their mere natural state (culture as spiritual formation). The Ancient World and the Middle Ages called this *humanitas, civilitas*. "Culture includes everything that is the result of man's conscious and free activity. It finds its proper end in the completion and perfection of man's nature" [3].

Origin, Meaning and Significance of Human Life

Life is a precious gift from God. It owes its origin from God Himself as the author of life, a life that begins at the moment of conception. As the book of Jeremiah asserts; "Before I formed you in the womb I knew you, before you were born I dedicated you". (Jer; 1:5)

In the African understanding, human life come from God through the Ancestors and spirits. Life is considered sacred, it is upheld in great reverence, since human life is sacred. Life is surrounded by religious rituals, eg., Ancestors were appealed for children and spirits were asked to protect them. Life which was of great value is safeguarded with prayers, magic ritual and protective charms. Human life was/is seen to be very fundamental and precious. Life is/was seen as a power, strength or energy or vital force. Life was a precious gift given to man and woman by God. Life was a very religious reality. Therefore, prayers and sacrifices were offered to God, to the spirits and Ancestors. Africans desired to have life and to transmit it to others through procreation, and this was considered to be a religious act.

To miss to procreate or transmit life for an African is to miss the joy of sharing in religious act. Hence, care for the aged is crucial for an African. Life in many African communities is founded on interaction between God, creation, and interpretation between the right and wrong. Thus whatever promotes and enhances life is good and vice versa. Life therefore means the whole round wellbeing (body and soul) against the powers of hatred, sickness and deaths. Man and woman are beneficiaries of this life through cosmos, parents, and clan. Life is not merely Biological but meta-empirical, that is not a fruit of physical conception. It is a most precious gift, a gift per excellence.

"African religion affirms life, and celebrates life a large number of rituals, festivals and ceremonies which are carried out in African religion. These all add up to the celebration of life. People know that they are alive. They want to celebrate the joy of the living. They do not seat down meditating upon life. Instead, they put it into action: they dance life, they sing life, the ritualize life, they shout life, they ceremonize life, they festivize life, for the individual and for the community" [8].

The Culture of Life

The declining on the culture of life has greatly threatened and damaged the human dignity in Africa. The increasing spread of destruction of human life has produced an ugly image to the face of the African continent.

"The value of human life springs from what is spiritual in man; the body receives from the spiritual principle-which... makes it what it is- a supreme dignity, a kind of reflection of the Absolute. The body is that of a person, a being which is open to superior values, a being capable of fulfilment in the knowledge of the love of God" [7].

The bodily life of human being is an exalted good. It is a life amidst the Earthly pilgrimage and as a unique thing that is a time of favor which a person is tried and tested. It is a time of growth in love of God and neighbor. During the bodily life time is time to give the best of oneself for best of oneself for benefit of human kind today and in the future generation. It is the time to implement love, joy, peace, goodness, and justice. If we assert that God is the author of life, it certainly follows that, one's existence is one's but at the same time God's property. Every finite being exist for one reason, only to manifest the goodness of God. Therefore, life is not to be disposed as one wishes. A person is unique and incalculable and is beyond human computation. He/she is '*imago Dei*'. Life of any person does not depend on any skill or any price tags or in what one can do/make/achieve but in what one 'is'. The meaning and purpose of one's creation and a continued existence lies in humans' unique image of God and in what one can do or make or actualize. This image, that is why one's existence should not be interfered at any stage or

state of life, that is poor or rich, young or old. Life tempering actions such as abortion and euthanasia should be firmly discouraged. Once created, human being has no right to temper with it. The purpose of our creation and existence gives us a greater dignity than that of Earthly beings. If we see this ourselves, then we must let our neighbor have the right to live as each person is unique and reputable being.

The Stewardship of Life

"Am I my brother's keeper? (*Gen 4:9*) - *Cain and perverse idea of freedom.*

From the dawn of creation, human being was endowed with a two-fold uniqueness; they bear God's image consisting of rational, moral, social and spiritual entities which helps him/her know God, and the dominion over other creatures. Therefore stewardship should not be exercised in a loveless attitude but in a spirit of reverence to one's life and life of others. This is mainly because we are not independent master of our life but steward subjects toward sovereignty of God. So if need be, just like Christ be ready to lay down our life for the service of others as witness to faith, love and hope.

Promoting the Culture of Life

Promoting the culture of life here means exalting, affirming and defending life, both to the unborn and the marginalized. It entails accepting and promoting the new life, including the ecosystem and repudiation of the atrocious and diabolic killing and all that leads to a culture of death. To repudiate all use of excessive armed force, and armed conflicts. To inculcate the inviolability of human life, to keep human beings safe from assault entails respecting the sacredness of human life from its beginning to its natural end.

The reason behind this trend of doctrine being that humanity owes their origin from God who is the creator and soul end. God alone is Lord of life from the beginning to the end. No human under any circumstance can claim to have a right to destroy life.

"Human life is sacred because from its beginning it involves the creative action of God and it remains forever in a special relationship with the creator, who is its soul end. God alone is the Lord of life from its beginning until its end: no one can under any circumstance claim for himself the right directly to destroy an innocent human being" [1].

Scripture reveals a presence of anger and envy from the dawn of creation. A person has become an enemy of his fellow human. God declared it a danger of fratricide. (*Gen, 4:10-11, 9:5-6*).

Scripture asserts "Thou shall not kill". This is a universal law and universally valid, it binds all and at all time and everywhere. This command encourages a positive attitude for respect of life. Killing/deliberate murder is contrary to: the dignity of human, to the golden rule, to the holiness of God. And therefore the Church considers murder amongst the three most serious sins,

the other two being adultery and apostasy. Because God is the author and Lord of life, human beings have the duty to respect it.

The Culture of Death

Death is expressed in various ways in Africa depending on the culture of a respective place. By the fact that people die many times such that burial occasions becomes part and parcel of life in their homestead, people regard it as a day to day experience. But as something which could be scrutinized, and avoided especially on the death causes that are not natural and untimely.

"When one talks of the culture of death, what comes to mind is abortion, euthanasia, murder, deadly violence, genocide, devil worship, drug trafficking, and addictions, numerous frequent land/sea/space/underground and fatal accidents, terrorism, HIV/AIDS, (Covid 19 Virus) ...The list is long. We have become so used to death that we hardly think about it" [12].

It is natural to experience a demise of every living being. That is what it entails death. Death is ceasing of life. It is a stopping of biological life.

"In general, death is a biological and physiological happening and so it affects all living corporeal things. It consists in the cessation of life. This end is expressed in the stopping of all life activities, i.e., growth, nutrition and propagation in the vegetative world" [3].

To an African, death is something impolite, sorrowful, since its work is to kill, destroy, take away, and terrorize people everywhere. "Death, also meant a separation of God from men. "Some think of it as a monster, others as an animal, and many regard it as a kind of spirit." [8] Death to an African marks a physical cut off of an individual from the entire society.

According to John Mbiti;

"Africans people refer to dying as returning home, going away, answering the summons, departing, ceasing to eat, ceasing to breath, sinking, fighting a losing battle, refusing food, rejecting people, sleeping, taking one way, saying goodbye, shutting the eyes, being broken up, being snatched away, being taken away being called away, joining the fore fathers, becoming Gods property, and so on" [8].

The idea of natural death is not overlooked by the African Philosophy scholars. Before we enter into theological analysis of death it is better to have a look on John Mbiti, an African scholar who asserts that:

"There are always physical causes and circumstances surrounding every death. These include sickness, disease, old age, accident, lightning, earthquake, flood, drowning, animal attack, and many others. But African peoples believe that a particular person will die from one of these physical causes because some human or other agents have brought it about by means of a curse, witchcraft, magic and so on" [8].

In theological context, human being encompasses a body and a soul. It follows necessarily that when the body dies it marks the inevitable separation of the two, as May asserts; "Theologically speaking, death occurs when the soul is separated from the body, for then the body is no longer a living human body, a person, but the mortal remains of a person." [7] To clearly know what death is for a Christian we must first seek to know how the pre-Christian, pagan antiquity regarded it before we turn to revelation. In the Ancient World the fact of death was one among the topic that gained attention. The provoking question that sparked a discussion was: "Why must this evil, this supreme punishment, visit him, who did no wrong? For when the gods created man, they let death be his share" [6].

The Egyptians spent a considerable good time to circumvent on the issue of death in asserting their hope in an eternally continuing life. In the Ancient Greece, however the realm of the dead was not something to be desired. "For the Greeks, like so many people of the Ancient World, believed that, somehow, death was not final, that the dead lived, in some dark and shady world, and unenviable form of attenuated life." [6]. In the OT narrative we see the piece of land purchased by Abraham in the Land to which the Lord called him was a 'cemetery plot'. "I am a stranger resident among you; give me burial ground among you that I may bury my dead". (Gen, 23:4). The burial of the dead was a duty to which the Israelites were bound in piety. A good burial was a right to every Israelite, even to the condemned criminal. The solicitude for the burial of the dead indicated that there was a destined place for them. "The dead, we are told, went down to 'Sheol' [6] which was the destined place for everyone alive. (Job, 30: 23). They were gathered to their ancestors; they went to their fathers in peace. (Gen, 15:5).

Death was considered to be a rest of an individual human being. "Do not burry me in Egypt, but let me rest with my fathers; carry me out of Egypt, and bury me in their sepulcher."(Gen, 47, 29-30). They compared death to the nether world, and the barren womb, the earth, that is never saturated with water, and fire, that never says, Enough". (Prov. 30:16). A question arises as to whether death was considered really final or not? Was there any hope beyond the grave? Was life on earth the only true life? Definitely yes, because we live to die and die to live, the hope beyond the grave remains fixed to the unshakable faith of a believer.

"Generally speaking, immortality was hoped for in its literal sense of deathlessness; and Enock who had been 'taken up' (Gen, 5:21ff.) and Elias who went up on a whirlwind into heaven. (4: Kings 2;11ff,) remained as types of that hoped - for fate." [6]. In the other perspective, death was closely linked with justice and the observance of the law, as we read below; "In the way of justice there is life, but the abominable way

leads to justice and observance of the law. - In the way of justice there is life, but the abominable way leads to death" (Prov. 12:28); Virtue directs toward life, but he who pursues evil does so to his death. (Prov. 11:19). Death in the OT, was seen as a punishment for the sinner that walked not in the way of the Lord.

"St. Ambrose sees death as a good thing feared only by the foolish" [6]. He distinguished three different senses of the word 'death', the death due to sin which is the state of soul deprived of God; mystical death, where by a person dies to sin, to live unto God; and the death which brings to a close of our earthly pilgrimage, which is the end of our life here on earth, the separation of our souls from our bodies. This reflection of St. Ambrose on death might have been reflecting on St. Paul's statement in Philippians, "To live is Christ, to die is gain" and especially on the death of his brother Satyrus. (Phil 1:21).

The Causes of Deaths in Africa

Death tolls in Africa varies from place, time to time and depends on a cause from which it occurs. As if there are no other causes of deaths, recently the attention of the population, and scientists in Africa and elsewhere have been on the Covid 19 virus pandemic. However, there are other several causes of deaths in Africa, such as malaria, HIV/AIDS, Cancer, Ebola, diarrhea, tuberculosis, diabetes mellitus, cirrhosis of the liver, meningitis and cholera. Other causes of deaths include, abortion deaths, hunger, genocide deaths, suicide and bombing deaths, and deaths by accidents.

Corona Virus and Its Impacts in Africa

"COVID - 19 was first detected in Wuhan in Central China in late 2019. Since then more than 106 million cases and 2.3 million deaths have been reported worldwide". The COVID - 19 disease caused by the virus was declared as a pandemic by the World Health Organization (WHO) on 11 March 2020 [13]. The initial evidence suggested that the infection has a high effective reproduction rate with older populations and those with underlying health conditions being at high risk of severe disease and death, thereby forcing numerous countries into temporary lockdowns to limit the spread of this air borne disease.

"According to WHO (World Health Organization), Corona virus disease (Covid - 19) is an infectious disease caused by newly discovered corona virus. Most people infected with COVID-19 virus will experience mild to moderate respiratory illness and recover without requiring special treatment. Older people, and those with underlying medical problems, like cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and cancer are most likely to develop serious illness" [14].

Africa experienced its first case on 14 February, in Egypt, and Covid-19 was declared a global pandemic on 12 March, 2019 which later spread across many other African nations within Months [13]. COVID - 19

pandemic has strained Africa's already fragile health care services rising concerns over excess deaths from other diseases plaguing the continent.

"Africa has recorded more than 2.4 million cases of COVID-19 and more than 57,000 deaths, according to the African Union's Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, with the lower percentage of deaths due to early and strict lockdown measures." [18].

Having seen the threat and the fatality rate of the Corona Virus World-wide, scientists had to take some arguent measures pertaining to the modes of transmission of the disease. The WHO in collaboration with its scientists' highlights on the preventive measures as follows:

"The Covid - 19 virus spreads primarily through droplets of saliva or discharge from the nose when an infected person coughs or sneezes, so it's important that... (people) practice respiratory etiquette (for example, by coughing into a flexed elbow). The best way to prevent and to slow down transmission is to be well informed about the COVID-19 virus, the disease it causes and how it spreads. Protect oneself and others from infection by washing hands or using alcohol based rub frequently and not touching your face." [14].

However, the other killer diseases such as malaria, tuberculosis, HIV/AIDS cannot be over looked. According to the research and statistics made recently; "Each year more than 400,000 people globally die of malaria- a preventable and treatable mosquito-borne disease. An estimated two thirds of deaths are among children under the age of five. Sub-Saharan Africa shoulders the heaviest burden, accounting for 94% of malaria deaths worldwide. Nigeria, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Tanzania, Niger, Burkina Faso accounted for up to half of world's malaria deaths in 2019" [14].

The delayed anti-malaria facilities and campaigns, like distribution of bed mosquito nets have delayed, and patients have been either delayed or unable to attend the clinics for fear of visiting a clinic. This fear has been attributed to either the lock-down in cases of Covid-19 positive diagnosis, or the failure to meet the diagnostic and medical expenses to be incurred due to poverty.

According to WHO, such disruptions of projects will certainly, result into more deaths due to malaria than the COVID-19 itself in Sub-Saharan Africa. Scientists predicted that the excess malaria mortality will certainly be bigger than that of COVID 19 in Sub-Saharan Africa.

"It is likely that excess malaria mortality is larger than direct COVID-19 mortality is larger than direct COVID-19 mortality, said Pedro Alonso, director of WHO's

Malaria program on World Malaria Day. In the year 2020, the WHO forecasted a 10% disruption in access to anti-malarial treatment that could lead to 19,000 additional deaths in Africa" [14].

According to BBC, "malaria kills around 800,000 people a year and is second only to tuberculosis in its impact on world health" [21]. It is said by scientists that malaria is found in 90 countries and infects one in 10 of the world's population mainly people living in Africa especially the Sub-Saharan Africa.

"Ninety percent of all malaria cases are in Sub-Saharan Africa where it is the main cause of death and major threat to child health. Worldwide, a child dies of malaria every 30 seconds. Pregnant women are also particularly vulnerable to the disease, which is curable if diagnosed early." [21].

According to Scientists the other killer disease that takes a lot of lives is in Africa is namely 'tuberculosis'¹. Tuberculosis is said to have killed 1.4 million people globally last year 2020, and is one of the top ten causes of deaths worldwide.

"More than 95% of TB deaths are in developing countries with South-East Asia accounting for 44% of deaths, followed by Sub-Saharan Africa with 25%. These include countries such as South Africa, Nigeria, the Democratic Republic of Congo, Tanzania, Mozambique, Ethiopia, Kenya, Uganda and Zimbabwe" [18].

Statistics shows that TB is not only a killer disease but it remains fatal when it is linked to COVID -19, just like the case of HIV/AIDS is in connection to COVID - 19. According to Forbes, the prevalence of HIV/AIDS is significantly higher in Sub-Saharan Africa and the availability of ART is lower. Because of this... the effects of Covid-19 on people living with HIV is an open increased risk of death [19].

"The results, published in Clinical Infectious Diseases by Forbes, shows a roughly 2-fold greater risk of Covid-19 mortality in people living with HIV" [19]. According to a research done by Forbes in South Africa, people living with HIV/AIDS infection who are receiving antiretroviral therapy, their HIV infection alone probably does not greatly increase their risk of COVID - 19 deaths. To a Christian, sickness and death caused by disease is to be handled in faith in Jesus Christ the suffering Messiah without losing faith in him who suffered until death on the cross.

"Jesus' death was the culmination of his suffering. There he hung on the cross, gaped at and mocked by his enemies, forsaken by his friends. At least on the cross Jesus had to struggle to hold on to God, who had not preserved him from death. Jesus' experience of

¹Tuberculosis is a potentially serious infectious bacterial disease that mainly affects the lungs, also called TB, partially preventable by vaccine, spreads by airborne droplets.

suffering was a comfort and an encouragement to the early Christians. It prevented them from repressing their suffering. It gave them the strength to endure their suffering in a hostile environment" [4].

Impact of Lock Down in Africa

Since the advent of COVID-19 pandemic, 'lock-down' has been one of the preventive measures taken by various countries. Due to the spreading of this air borne virus, famously known as COVID 19 there has been some health impacts associated with the lockdown which emerged as a result of isolation, public health emergencies, stigma, job insecurity, or inadequate resources for medical response. Fear, anxiety, emotional distress, post trauma stress symptoms just to mention a few of them, have been the effects of the lock-down due to COVID-19. The question arises, for how long should the lock-down take place if statistics of the infection keeps growing. Is lock-down alone reliable solution? To prevent its spread, many cities, regions and countries were or have been locked down, shutting down economic and social activities.

"In response to the COVID-19 outbreak, many countries in Sub Saharan Africa followed the same strategy as high income countries and have implemented strict lockdown measures to contain the spread of the virus. Some countries have imposed business closures, others have severely restricted public and private transport or have closed their borders. 55% of sub-Saharan countries we could gather data for have ordered businesses to close, and a further 17% of them have advised work places to close... we estimate that containment measures in sub-Saharan Africa, in their current form, have pushed an additional 9.1% of the population into extreme poverty" [16].

Covid-19 Death Tolls and the Puzzle of the Vaccine

It is obviously observed that COVID - 19 virus has/ is still taking the lives of many Africans. In Tanzania alone the "TBC, (Tanzania Broadcasting Corporation) BBC, and Aljazeera reported cases of COVID - 19, hospitalizations and deaths." [15]. According to the latest news, from Aljazeera, President Samia Suluhu Hassan, the President of the Republic of Tanzania, is said to have given a hint at a major changes of policy on COVID - 19, which shows that the COVID-19 exists and still kills.

This is an indication already that there is still a need for citizens to take preventive measures such a wearing masks, keeping distance, - social distancing is necessary to slow the spread. "Stay at least 6 feet (about 2 arm's length from other people, do not gather in large groups. Stay out of crowded places and avoid mass gatherings. Wash hands with running water, wash often using soap

and water at least for 20 seconds, and as an option use hand sanitizer, that means alcohol based when washing is not possible. Clean and disinfect often; with a house hold cleaning product, wipe frequently touched objects or regularly used surfaces. Staying home when one is sick, not to expose it to others and wearing face masks. People interacting in other proximity should wear a cloth face covering in public settings when social distancing of at least 6 feet cannot be maintained" [17]. Many questions arise when we tackle the issue of the pandemic. Such questions are like: Is there any hope for a reliable vaccine? Which vaccine to take, ASTRA ZENECA, "Johnson and Johnson"², or some other vaccines? What if one is vaccinated and dies right after that, will there be any compensation? Who has to take the first shot of vaccine before it is declared a reliable vaccine, is it the Africans?

One should not imagine that COVID -19 has been spoken too much in this article, but by the fact that COVID -19 is the current burning issue, there is a need for a thorough and attentive investigation into the issue before we lose our 'dear life'. It is good to know and accept the reality of the natural death of human beings like that of old age as something that has to come at someday in the future days and that it will certainly interfere with this bodily life.

"The contemporary World has lost sight of the truth about the meaning and value of human life-which God impressed on the conscience of man ever since creation- and with it the full significance of old age and death. Today death has lost its sacred character- its sense of fulfilment. It has become a taboo. Every effort is made to sweep it under the carpet, to make sure that it does not disturb" [9].

Hope Beyond the Grave

"I am the resurrection and the life; whoever believes in me, even if he dies, will live, and everyone who lives and believes in me will never die". (Jn, 11:25-26.) From the Roman Catholic Missal, we encounter a consoling truth about death which highlights an eschatological dimension of the life after death as something real to those who believe in God, this idea has its foundation in the Scriptures as one of Jesus' profound teaching.

"Numbed by the daily images of death presented in the media, people today do everything in their power to avoid coming to terms with a reality which causes them only distress, anxiety and fear" [9].

Africa need to implement a good system that will facilitate good health services. And understand that this alone may not be solution if the entire people do not take the necessary precautions with regard to

² In 26 July2021, Tanzania received first COVID - 19, vaccine batch. Over 1 Million Johnson and Johnson vaccine doses arrived on Saturday from US. Cf., <https://www.un.org>, (accessed on 26, November, 2023).

contagious diseases, balance diet, and hygiene etc. Building of hospitals, preparation of scientists as a working force and improved conditions of livelihood for them could mean much for the African countries. This empowering of the health sectors will for sure encourage innovations and will encourage creativity. African medical scientists should not opt to work abroad but strive to improve the working conditions within their African territories, otherwise, Africa will always experience brain draining of her scientists and will witness an exodus of her learned experts looking for green pasture abroad.

Even when death occurs, as it obviously has to happen; there should not be any negative fatalism about it.

"In the light of these words, death-no longer a condemnation, no longer a meaningless epilogue of life signifying nothing-is revealed as time of hope; the true and certain hope of coming face to face with the Lord" [9].

Life is Worthy Living

A couple of questions arise when we come toward the end of our essay. Does life have a meaning? Is it not monotony? Should we live to last a hundred and fifteen years? Such questions and others left can stir up a great discussion on whether our struggle to live should disregard the lives of others, those already born and the unborn babies. Life is monotonous if it has no purpose. "Life is monotonous if it has no goal or purpose. When we do not know why we are here or where we are going, then life is full of frustrations and unhappiness. When there is no goal or overall purpose, people generally concentrate on motion. Instead of working toward an ideal, they keep changing the ideal and calling it progress." [10].

Fear of Death (*thanatophobia*) Paralyzing the Courage to Live.

"But the souls of the righteous are in the hands of God, and no torment will ever touch them. In the eyes of the foolish they seemed to have died, and their departure was thought to be an affliction. For though in the sight of men they were punished, their hope is full of immortality."(Wis, 3:1- 4). It is crucial to contemplate about death and our own reactions on it and to the mysterious reality of eternal life.

"In fact, the Christian should never even think of physical death alone but always in conjunction with eternal life. For us it should be as if as if these two mysteries are each halves of the same whole, two sides of the same coin; they should be as inseparable in our minds as they are in Gods' plan of redemption for us. This is essential, for death considered alone is a sorrow; in fact, it can even be a horror. Death alone -without the possibility of eternal life- is an irrevocable end" [2]. As true Christians who believe in the risen Christ and victor, we must face death with all prayerful courage and the calmness of mind and heart. We must be true

Christians and see into eternity. This is because without eternal life our earthly lives are reduced to sad mysteries-pointless mysteries that are constantly fading into nothingness.

What can Africa Learn from COVID -19 Experience?

It is difficult to explain as to why the death tolls due to COVID - 19 in Europe outnumbered those in Africa. Still yet Africa lost a lot of its people due to COVID - 19. The Corona virus is here with us; we live with it as it is to other pandemics. The question comes on what lesson can African nations learn from the COVID - 19.

"The COVID - 19 pandemic taught Africans a lot about the system they are building and how it is not sustainable" [13]. Africans still depend on Europe and Middle Eastern countries in medical facilities, experts and technology. "The lesson we have learned from the COVID - 19 pandemic underscore the importance of implementing effective policies to improve food environments, encourage physical activity, and protect the health and well-being of families" [14]. In Tanzania, during the time of serious COVID - 19 deaths it was reported that other pandemics like Cholera were not as serious as it were before COVID. This is to mean that hygienic instructions of washing hands using running water were highly followed and since then it have been a culture.

Tanzania can learn several important lessons from the experience of the COVID - 19 pandemic that may enhance its public health response and preparedness for future health crisis. The pandemic exposed weakness in healthcare systems worldwide. Tanzania can invest in strengthening its healthcare infrastructure, including hospitals, clinics, and laboratories, ensuring they are well equipped for emergencies.

Effective surveillance and systems and data collection are crucial for monitoring diseases outbreaks. Tanzania can still improve its health data infrastructure to facilitate timely responses and better allocation of resources.

The importance of clear, accurate, and consistent communication during health crisis was pivotal. Tanzania can still develop strategies for effective communication that engage the public and build trust in health authorities. The pandemic highlighted the importance of preventive health measures. Tanzania can promote vaccination, hygiene practices, and public health campaigns to address both infectious and non-infectious communicable diseases.

It required collaboration beyond the health sector, involving education, transformation, and social services. Strengthening inter-sectoral collaboration can enhance overall resilience to future pandemics. Investing in local research and integrating traditional medicines can help Tanzania build capacity to respond to health emergencies and create a home-made

solutions tailored to its unique contexts. Africa need African solutions to African problems. There is a need for emphasizing research and innovations.

Conclusion

A good Christian should know that the sorrows of this life are not worthy to be compared with the joy reserved for us in the life to come. Pain has a double reaction; one of which is rebellion and the other can be resignation. Those who rebel against it see no purpose in pain; but those who see it in relation to eternal salvation turn pain into what is creative. God is the life giver of every being on earth. If human beings stay united with God in faith under his wings, he will guide them.

Death can no longer be understood as perpetual lockdown of human life but as vital spring board into everlasting vitality. Life in this case transcends death by being transformed into eternity. Even at this age of disrespectful of other human life. When some human beings decide on 'who lives and who dies' with a purpose of overpopulation of the continents, or for whatever reason, since the value of human life remains intact - not something to temper with, and must be preserved and respected. The numerous causes of deaths toll in Africa and Tanzania in particular alerts us to recover the lost sight of truth about the meaning of human life which God impressed on humans' conscience since creation. Work untiringly to look for ways that can improve life expectancy, improve health facilities and train medical professionals, and encourage laboratory scientific innovations. Africa being a rich continent with variety of mineral resources and an extensive arable land can still make a difference. Africans should think of having that ability to produce her own vaccines for any future pandemics.

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